

D1.3 Proposal for grand instrument defined

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Executive summary

This deliverable reports on the proposal developed by UiO and SINTEF to access Grand Instrument, as defined in WINNER plan. The targeted study is summarized here. The near-ambient pressure scanning photoelectron microscope (NAP-SPEM) setup at Elettra will be used to perform operando studies of model electrodes based on $\text{BaGd}_{0.3}\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Co}_2\text{O}_{6-\delta}$ (BGLC), which is one of the best air/steam electrode materials available for Proton Ceramic Electrochemical Cells. The reduction and oxidation of H_2O and O_2 happen at the gas-electrode-electrolyte triple-phase boundary (tpb) and at the BGLC surface. The extension of the reaction zone from the tpb and outward on the electrode surface is not yet known. The red-ox reactions are facilitated by Co, which provide electrons and electron holes to the cathodic and anodic half-reactions, respectively. Thus, Co is expected to deviate from its +3 oxidation state at the surface during operation. Interdigitated model electrodes of BGLC deposited on a $\text{BaZr}_{0.4}\text{Ce}_{0.4}\text{Y}_{0.2}\text{O}_3$ (BZCY) electrolyte will be studied. The oxidation state of Co across 70-100 μm wide electrode strips will be monitored by NAP-SPEM while performing Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) under anodic and cathodic bias in a mixture of O_2 and H_2O gas at elevated temperatures (400 – 600°C). The reaction zone will be mapped based on Co oxidation state, and while the electrostatic potential will give a uniform distribution of Co-species over the electrode, we predict a gradual change over the reaction zone. Our hypothesis is that the extension of the electrochemically active area of the electrode is changed as a function of applied current density, which calls for analysis tools with the spatial resolution of the SPEM technique. The potential outcome of the experiments will be a ground-breaking progression in the understanding of high temperature electrodes, electrode reactions and -materials.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Presentation of WINNER

The WINNER project aims to develop an efficient and durable technology platform based on electrochemical proton conducting ceramic (PCC) cells designed for unlocking a path towards commercially viable production, extraction, purification and compression of hydrogen at small to medium scale. This will be demonstrated in WINNER in three applications: ammonia cracking, dehydrogenation of hydrocarbons, and reversible steam electrolysis. By such, WINNER will create innovative solutions for flexible, secure and profitable storage and utilization of energy in the form of hydrogen and green ammonia, electrification of the chemical industry and sectors coupling.

The WINNER project builds on the pioneering multidisciplinary expertise of world leading partners in the fields of proton conducting ceramic (PCC) materials and technologies to combine materials science, multi-scale multi-physics modelling and advanced in-situ and operando characterisation methods to unveil unprecedented performance of tubular PCC cells assembled in a flexible multi-tube module operating at industrially relevant conditions. WINNER will develop innovative cell architectures with multifunctional electrodes and a novel pressure-less current collection system using eco-friendly and scalable manufacturing routes.

Figure 1 WINNER concept focusing on novel materials, electrodes, current collection, and assemblies for three main applications

The experimental activities will be steered by a novel multi-scale multi-physics modelling platform and enhanced experimentation methodologies. These tools combined with advanced operando and in situ methods will serve at establishing correlations between performance and degradation mechanisms associated with both materials properties and interface's evolution upon operation. Testing of cells and modules will also be conducted to define performance and durability in various operation modes. Techno-economic assessment of the novel PCC processes will be conducted as well as Life Cycle Assessment. The project is coordinated by SINTEF with support from University of

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Oslo, Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Cientificas (CSIC-ITQ), Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DTU), Aktiebolaget Sandvik Materials Technology, CoorsTek Membrane Sciences AS, ENGIE, Shell Global Solutions International B.V.

1.2 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable reports on the proposal prepared by UiO and SINTEF for accessing to the near-ambient pressure scanning photoelectron microscope (NAP-SPEM) facility enabling combined Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) under anodic and cathodic bias in a mixture of O₂ and H₂O gas at elevated temperatures (400 – 600°C). The proposal has been submitted in March 2022, and is reported below.

2 Proposal

ELETTRA PROPOSAL DESCRIPTION

Proposal number: 20220084

Title: Mechanistic understanding of intermediate temperature proton ceramic electrochemical cells through operando scanning photoelectron microscopy.

Proposer: Ingvild Julie Thue JENSEN

Beamline(s) requested: ESCAMICROSCOPY

Shifts requested: 18

Abstract: The near-ambient pressure scanning photoelectron microscope (NAP-SPEM) setup at Elettra will be used to perform operando studies of model electrodes based on BaGd_{0.3}La_{0.7}Co₂O_{6-δ} (BGLC), which is one of the best air/steam electrode materials available for Proton Ceramic Electrochemical Cells. The reduction and oxidation of H₂O and O₂ happen at the gas-electrode-electrolyte triple-phase boundary (tpb) and at the BGLC surface. The extension of the reaction zone from the tpb and outward on the electrode surface is not yet known. The red-ox reactions are facilitated by Co, which provide electrons and electron holes to the cathodic and anodic half-reactions, respectively. Thus, Co is expected to deviate from its +3 oxidation state at the surface during operation. Interdigitated model electrodes of BGLC deposited on a BaZr_{0.4}Ce_{0.4}Y_{0.2}O₃ (BZCY) electrolyte will be studied. The oxidation state of Co across 70-100 μm wide electrode strips will be monitored by NAP-SPEM while performing Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) under anodic and cathodic bias in a mixture of O₂ and H₂O gas at elevated temperatures (400 – 600°C). The reaction zone will be mapped based on Co oxidation state, and while the electrostatic potential will give a uniform distribution of Co-species over the electrode, we predict a gradual change over the reaction zone. Our hypothesis is that the extension of the electrochemically active area of the electrode is changed as a function of applied current density, which calls for analysis tools with the spatial resolution of the SPEM technique. The potential outcome of the experiments will be a ground-breaking progression in the understanding of high temperature electrodes, electrode reactions and materials.

1. Scientific background: The proposed measurements will be part of two ongoing projects addressing the fundamental concepts of steam/air electrodes for Proton Ceramic Electrochemical Cells (PCECs) operated at intermediate temperatures (300-650 °C). PCECs, which interconvert electrical energy and chemical energy, represent an emerging technology for cost-efficient stationary energy storage, power generation and fuel production with excellent electrical efficiency,¹ as illustrated in Fig. 1. They integrate proton conducting oxides, serving as electrolytes and as electrocatalyst supports tailored towards the device applications. Proton-

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conducting oxides have several unique characteristics that distinguish them from both higher temperature oxide-ion conducting oxides and lower temperature proton-conducting polymers, by enabling **proton-mediated electrochemistry under both dry and wet environments at moderate temperatures (e.g. 300–650 °C)**.

Figure 1: Schematics of PCEC applications ranging from power generation (a), hydrogen production (b), and Power-to-X exemplified with CH_4 (c) and NH_3 (d) production. Reproduced and altered with permission from [1].

Significant efforts on the optimization of composition and fabrication of the state-of-the-art proton conducting electrolyte BZCY ($\text{BaZr}_{1-x-y}\text{Ce}_x\text{Y}_y\text{O}_{3-\delta}$) and PCEC electrodes such as $\text{BaGd}_{1-x}\text{La}_x\text{Co}_2\text{O}_{6-\delta}$ (BGLC) have led to impressive performance of PCECs operating as fuel-flexible fuel cellsⁱⁱ and electrolyzers.^{iii,iv} The current understanding of PCECs is still restricted to near-equilibrium conditions (i.e. open-circuit conditions) – and is thus not capable of describing the electrochemistry of PCECs as they are operated *far-from-equilibrium*. Studies to understand and improve the bulk defect chemistry and transport properties of electrolyte and electrode materials at equilibrium have resulted in the development of state-of-the-art O_2 - H_2O PCEC electrodes based on mixed-cation perovskites with protonic and electronic conductivity.^{v,vi} Dedicated studies on the mechanisms for proton incorporation and diffusion in these typically p-type conducting perovskites have revealed a significant inter-play between the oxidation state of the material and the affinity for proton incorporation, due to both proton-hole defect interactions and changes to the overall defect concentrations and available oxygen vacancies for hydration. Thus it is expected that the electrocatalytic properties of the electrode materials is altered when operated out-of-equilibrium. **However, the link from the thermodynamic bulk properties measured under equilibrium conditions to the electrochemical and kinetic activity of the electrode surface as the system is driven away from equilibrium is still missing.**

2. Motivation for the proposal: $\text{BaGd}_{0.3}\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Co}_2\text{O}_{6-\delta}$ (BGLC) is one of the best air/steam electrode materials for Proton Ceramic Electrochemical Cells (PCEC's), comprising Fuel Cells (PEFC's) and Electrolyzers (PCE's). BGLC is a triple conducting ceramic, facilitating bulk transport of protons, oxide ions and electrons/electron holes. In the anodic and cathodic reactions, H_2O and O_2 are reduced and oxidised, facilitated by the Co atoms in the perovskite B-position. The red-ox reactions happen at the BGLC surface and at the gas-electrode-electrolyte triple-phase boundary (tpb). Since Co is providing electrons and electron holes to the cathodic and anodic half-reactions, respectively, **Co will deviate from its +3 oxidation state at the surface when the cell is operated under bias.** The electrode reactions may be investigated by Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) during operation, but **the extension of the reaction zone from the tpb and outward on the electrode surface is not yet investigated.** Also the dependence of the reaction zone extension on increasing current is unknown. Our proposal is to design interdigitated model electrodes of BGLC deposited on a $\text{BaZr}_{1-x-y}\text{Ce}_x\text{Y}_y\text{O}_3$ (BZCY) electrolyte by a combination of Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD) and photolithography and **monitor the oxidation state of Co across 70-100 μm wide electrode strips while performing EIS under anodic and cathodic bias.** The reaction zone will be mapped based on average Co oxidation state, and while the electrostatic potential itself will give a uniform distribution

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of Co-species over the electrode, we predict a gradual change over the reaction zone where the half-cell reactions will entail Co oxidation state to decrease and increase for anodic and cathodic operation, respectively. Scanning over two electrode strips with opposite potential, it will be possible to map out how the two half-reactions and their accompanying electrostatic potentials will affect Co oxidation state differently.

3. Experimental plan: Atmospheric operation at high temperature is a requirement to ensure sufficiently high reaction rates, and the system will be studied in a mixture of O_2 and H_2O at high temperatures (400 – 600°C). Increased H_2O concentration from 2.5 – 50% - while keeping pO_2 constant (balance with N_2) will give information about the limiting kinetic reaction steps, highlighting the effect of water on the anode and cathode. The sample geometry will be based on a model electrode system with interdigitated electrodes with fixed geometry, see Fig. 2. For each atmospheric condition (temperature, pO_2 and pH_2O), spatially resolved XPS analysis will be performed across the width of each electrode "finger" from the edge (at the triple-phase-boundary) as a function of current density (controlled with a potentiostat). Peak shape analysis of the Co LMM and 3p peaks will be used for the determination of the Co oxidation state. This should provide information on any changes in the surface chemistry and/or Co valence state of the electrode material while in electrochemical operation – and the distance at which this change is apparent. The latter will thus provide direct evidence of extension of the electrochemical reaction away from the triple-phase-boundary. The electrodes will be analyzed electrochemically prior to the measurements to establish the specific current densities of interest, but we estimated ≥ 5 different current-steps at each condition.

Figure 2: Schematic outline of the electrode design, with the SPEM field-of-view illustrated to the left.

4. Justification of beamline(s) and beamtime requested Photoemission spectroscopy is a valuable tool for investigation of the surface chemistry of electrode materials and identification of any changes in Co valence states while under electrochemical operation, but standard lab-scale instruments have limited spatial resolution and usually operate in UHV. Our hypothesis is that the extension of the electrochemical active area of the electrode is changed as a function of applied current density, which calls for analysis tools with the spatial resolution of the SPEM technique. At the NAP-SPEM setup at the Elettra synchrotron high resolution, operando photoemission spectroscopy can be performed during gas exposure. It is of great scientific interest to investigate the samples at closer-to-realistic conditions to improve the mechanistic understanding of PCECs. The NAP-SPEM measurements will be complimented by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy and surface exchange kinetics measurements to provide a complete picture of the electrode reaction mechanisms. The requested 6 days of beamtime allows a full characterization of the electrode behaviour across the experimental matrix (T, pO_2 and pH_2O).

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5. Results Expected & Impact: Successful realization of *operando* understanding of electrochemical processes in PCECs that couple equilibrium thermodynamics with kinetics and electrochemistry will represent a significant scientific breakthrough in the field of protonics. The outcome of the experiments will be a ground-breaking progression in the understanding of high temperature electrodes, electrode reactions and -materials. It will also be a direct study of the link between the states of electrons and electron holes and the rates of electrochemical reactions. Furthermore, the mapping of reaction zone extension versus increasing bias will enable the design of optimal microstructures for increased electrode performance. The study will give direct input to electrochemical theory, making it possible to obtain analytical solutions for DC current-voltage relations over the electrode-electrolyte-gas interphase.

6. References related to the proposal scientific text:

ⁱ Serra, J. M. *Nature Energy* **4**, 178-179, doi:10.1038/s41560-019-0353-y (2019)

ⁱⁱ Duan, C. *et al. Science* **349**, 1321-1326 (2015).

ⁱⁱⁱ Choi, S. *et al. Nature Energy*, doi:10.1038/s41560-017-0085-9 (2018).

^{iv} Vøllestad, E. *et al. Nature Materials*, 2019

^v Strandbakke, R. *et al., Solid State Ionics* **278**, 120-132, doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ssi.2015.05.014 (2015).

^{vi} Zohourian, R., Merkle, R. & Maier, J. *Solid State Ionics* **299**, 64-69 (2017).